

APPENDIX D

Virtual agents example

As is described in Section 3.2, the conversations are assigned with a score between 0 to 3 points, where 0 indicates that there is no presence of the skill and 3 that the skill is achieved outstandingly. In this case, the message "select your stars" is not a message that asks or delivers relevant information to make a plan to solve the problem, rather it can be considered a mandatory order, even though the student does not know what solution they will implement, nor what star they will choose. Therefore, the agents will respond with a certain coherence and with intentions of recovering by giving another opportunity to the student to collaborate (Table D.1).

Table D.1

Virtual Agent Messages Example C1 Skill

Turn	Student 1	Agent 1	Agent 2
1	<i>Select your stars</i>		
2		<i>I do not know which stars we should choose</i>	
3			<i>Does anyone else know what to choose?</i>
4	<i>If we select the stars ##, ## and ##, we form the same objective constellation, because it has the same colors and order.</i>		
5		<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>	
6			<i>I'm going to choose the stars ## and ##</i>
7	<i>Yes, I agree.</i>	<i>Yes, I agree XX.</i>	

Note: The symbols ## are replaced by a selector in the interface, which allows the user to select a number between 1 to 46, corresponding to the index of the star or atom of which he is speaking. XX is replaced by the interface by the name of student 1